

**STREAMLINED GERIATRIC AND ONCOLOGICAL EVALUATION BASED ON
IC TECHNOLOGY
FOR HOLISTIC PATIENT-ORIENTED HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT
FOR OLDER MULTIMORBID PATIENTS**

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GERONTE Consortium

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6	E-Seniors	ESE	FR
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9	International Society of Geriatric Oncology	SIOG	CH
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History of Changes

Version	Date	Author	Description of change
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Executive Summary

The present document corresponds to the deliverable D4.2 “Trial committees’ charters” of the GERONTE project, which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement N° 945218. These charters will describe memberships, roles and responsibilities of the Trial Steering Committee (oversight body for the trials on behalf of the sponsor) and the Trial Management Team (set-up to carry out day-to-day management of the trials).

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as described in Annexe 1 (Description of the Action Part A) of the Grant Agreement N°945218.

Justification for delay in deliverable submission

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved on time and as scheduled in Annexe 1 (Description of the Action Part A) of the Grant Agreement N°945218.

Glossary

CTU	Clinical Trials Unit
TMT	Trial Management Team
TSC	Trial Steering Committee

1. Introduction

1.1. GERONTE and its objectives

GERONTE is a 5-year research and innovation project (April 2021 to Mars 2026) funded by the European Union within the framework of the H2020 Research and Innovation programme, in response to the health societal challenge topic SC1-BHC-24-2020 “Healthcare interventions for the management of the elderly multimorbid patient”. The overall aim of GERONTE is to improve quality of life - defined as well-being on three levels: global health status, physical functioning and social functioning- for older multimorbid patients, while reducing overall costs of care. To this end, GERONTE will co-design, test, and prepare for deployment an innovative cost-effective patient-centred holistic health management system, hereafter referred to as the GERONTE intervention. GERONTE intervention will rely on an ICT based application (Holis™) for real-time collection and integration of standardised clinical and home patient-reported data. GERONTE intervention will be demonstrated in the context of care of multimorbid patients having cancer as a dominant morbidity, and be adaptable to any other combination of morbidities.

Objectives

O1: INFORMATION gather the stakeholders and data needed for patient-centred and multi-actor complex decision-making process and management

O2: TOOLS develop ICT tools for the GERONTE intervention to be implemented

O3: METHODS develop socio-economic methods for evaluating the impacts of the implementation of the GERONTE intervention

O4: DEMONSTRATION demonstrate in 16 study sites from three EU countries the feasibility and effectiveness of the GERONTE intervention

O5: REPLICATION develop recommendations for the replication of GERONTE best practices in all European health systems

O6: ENGAGEMENT engage all stakeholders by co-designing the GERONTE intervention

1.2. Rationale

The current work corresponds to deliverable D4.2, which is part of work-package 4, which supports GERONTE objective 3 “Demonstration and validation”. The objective of WP4 is to perform two clinical trials, i.e. FRONE in France and TWOBE in Belgium and the Netherlands, in accordance with ethical and regulatory requirements. The goal is to provide a Proof of Concept of the GerOnTe model in three distinct European countries, and (i) to provide data on how the GerOnTe intervention fits into different health organisation systems, and (ii) to quantify the effectiveness and efficiency of GerOnTe system.

2. Trial Steering Committee (TSC) charter

The purpose of the TSC charter is to describe the membership, terms of reference, roles, responsibilities, authority, decision-making and relationships of the TSC for GERONTE trials, including the timing, frequency and format of meetings, methods of providing information to and from the TSC and relationships with other trial committees.

The TSC Charter is detailed in Appendix 1.

3. Trial Management Team (TMT) charter

The Trial Management Team (TMT) is the operational team that undertakes the day-to-day management of the GERONTE trials.

The TMT Charter is detailed in Appendix 2.

APPENDIX 1: Trial Steering Committee (TSC) charter

Trial Steering Committee (TSC) charter

Version 0.1 du 29/03/2022

GERONTE consortium FRONE and TWOBE Trials

Sponsors: Institut Bergonié (FRONE) and Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (TWOBE)

Coordinating Investigators: Pierre Soubeyran and Hans Wildiers

NCT: TBD at submission

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Clinical Trials Unit (CTU): EUCLID

Writing / Update	EUCLID CTU Project manager Dr Cécile Duchiron	Signature
Validation	EUCLID CTU representative Dr Christine Schwimmer Sponsor representative Pr Simone Mathoulin-Pelissier	Signature Signature
Approbation	Coordinating investigator FRONE trial: Pr Pierre Soubeyran TWOBE trial: Pr Hans Wildiers	Signature
Dissemination	TSC members	

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Charter	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • approve / comment on any abstracts and presentations of any results <i>during and after</i> the running of the trials • approve/comment any external communication on the trials, including press release to the lay public • approve external or early internal requests for release of data or subsets of data including clinical data.
3. Before or early in the trial	
Whether members of the TSC will have a contract	TSC members will not be asked to formally sign a contract but should formally register their agreement to join the group by confirming (1) that they agree to be a member of the TSC and (2) that they agree with the contents of this Charter. Any potential competing interests should be declared at the same time. Members should complete and return the form in Appendix 2. Any observers (attendees who are not members) will sign a confidentiality agreement on the first occasion they attend a meeting (Appendix 2).
4. Composition	
Membership of the TSC	The membership will be made up of voting and non-voting members, permanent invited observers and invited observers (Appendix 1). The charter will be amended for each modification of the membership. New agreement corresponding to the new version of the charter will be signed only for modification concerning voting-members.
Tenure	TSC members are nominated for the entire duration of the study. However, if for any reason they need to end their participation, they will be replaced.
The responsibilities of the Facilitator	The TSC Facilitator will be responsible for arranging meetings of the TSC, coordinating reports, producing and circulating minutes and action points. The Facilitator will be the central point for all TSC communications between the TSC and other trial bodies, will be copied into all correspondence between TSC members, and will be kept aware of trial issues as they arise.
The responsibilities of the observers	Observers may be in attendance through the TSC meetings in order to provide input on behalf of the Trial Management Team, the sites, the trial's Sponsors or to provide specific relevant expertise. Ad hoc observers may be invited as needed.

Charter	
5. Relationships	
<p>Relationships with Coordinating investigators, other trial committee (TMT), Sponsors and regulatory bodies</p> <p>The need for TSC members to disclose information about any real or potential competing interests</p>	<p>The responsibilities of each trial committee are detailed in the protocol and in the respective Charters.</p> <p>Any competing interests, both real and/or potential, should be disclosed. These are not restricted to financial matters – involvement in other trials or intellectual investment could be relevant. Although members may well be able to act objectively despite such connections, complete disclosure enhances credibility. (See Appendix 2)</p>
6. Organisation of meetings	
<p>Expected frequency of TSC meetings</p> <p>Attendance of TSC members at meetings</p> <p>How TSC meetings will be organised, especially regarding open and closed sessions, including who will be present in each session</p>	<p>The TSC will meet at least yearly face-to-face or via conference calls every 6 months. At the request of the TSC or sponsors, interim meetings, in person or by teleconference, can be organised at any time. Major trials issues may need to be dealt with between meetings, by phone or by email. TSC members should be prepared for such instances.</p> <p>Effort will be made for all members to attend. The TSC Facilitator will try and identify a date that enables this.</p> <p>For Face-to-Face meetings, attendance will be recorded by participant signatures on the attendance list prepared by the TSC Facilitator. Otherwise, attendance will be recorded in the TSC report.</p> <p>If the TSC is considering a major action, the TSC Chair, assisted by the TSC Facilitator, should communicate any decision to the absent members as soon as possible after the meeting. If they do not agree with the decision made, a teleconference should be arranged with the full TSC.</p> <p>Generally, the TSC should be able to reach a decision by consensus. However, rarely, if there is strong disagreement amongst the TSC members, then this should be resolved by means of a vote. All TSC members should participate in the TSC discussions but only voting members should cast a vote.</p> <p>Presence will be usually limited to the TSC members, permanent observers, and the TSC Facilitator. Other attendees may be invited for all or part of the meeting by the TSC. The observers are not members of the TSC but may be invited to provide expert input; other observers</p>

Charter

9. After the trial

<p>Publication of results</p> <p>The information about the TSC that will be included in published trial reports</p>	<p>The TSC will oversee the timely analysis, writing up and publication of the main trials results.</p> <p>TSC members will be named and their affiliations listed in the main report, unless they explicitly request otherwise. This will be done in compliance with GERONTE trials publication policy, which is approved by the TSC.</p>
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10. Definitions and abbreviations

GERONTE	Streamlined geriatric and oncological evaluation based on IC technology for holistic patient-oriented healthcare management for older multimorbid patients
TMT	Trial Management Team
TSC	Trial Steering Committee

11. Appendices

Appendix 1 – Composition of the Trial Steering Committee

Appendix 2 – Agreement and competing interests form for TSC members

Appendix 3 – Agreement and competing interests form for observers

APPENDIX 1 – Composition of the Trial Steering Committee

Role	Name	Institution
Voting Members		
Coordinating investigator FRONE, and consortium chair - Chair	Pierre Soubeyran	Institut Bergonié, FRANCE
Coordinating investigator TWOBE, Co-chair	Hans Wildiers	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, BELGIUM
Principal investigator NL, geriatric expert	Marije Hamaker	Stichting Diaconessenhuis, Utrecht, NETHERLANDS
Geriatrician independent member	Suzanne Festen	University Medical Centre Groningen, Groningen, NETHERLANDS
Methodologist independent member	Florence Canoui-Poitrine	AP-HP Hôpital Henri Mondor, Paris, FRANCE
Oncologist , independent member	Nicolo Battisti	The Royal Marsden Hospital, London, UNITED KINGDOM
Sponsor representative - Head of “Sponsor Department”	Simone Mathoulin Pelissier	Institut Bergonié, FRANCE
Sponsor representative	<i>Pending</i>	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, BELGIUM
Trials Methodologist	Florence Saillour-Glenisson	EUCLID, Bordeaux, FRANCE University of Bordeaux, FRANCE University Hospital of Bordeaux, FRANCE
EUCLID CTU representative	Christine Schwimmer	EUCLID, Bordeaux, FRANCE University of Bordeaux, FRANCE University Hospital of Bordeaux, FRANCE
Non-voting Members		
Sub-study leader ""	Lucia Ferrara	Universita Commerciale Luigi Bocconi, Milano, ITALY
Sub-study leader ""	Anthony Staines	University College Dublin, University of Ireland, Dublin, IRELAND
Trials Statistician	Marion Kret	EUCLID, Bordeaux, FRANCE University of Bordeaux, FRANCE University Hospital of Bordeaux, FRANCE
Patients representative	<i>Pending</i>	
MyPL representative	<i>Pending</i>	
TSC Facilitator, EUCLID project manager	Cécile Duchiron	EUCLID, Bordeaux, FRANCE University of Bordeaux, FRANCE Institut Bergonié, FRANCE
Permanent invited observers		
EUCLID senior Project Manager	Caroline Lalet	EUCLID, Bordeaux, FRANCE Institut Bergonié, FRANCE
EUCLID junior Methodologist	Julie Arsandaux	EUCLID, Bordeaux, FRANCE University of Bordeaux, FRANCE

EUCLID representative	Cédric WALLET	EUCLID, Bordeaux, FRANCE University of Bordeaux, FRANCE University Hospital of Bordeaux, FRANCE
KUL representative	Lien Degol	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, BELGIUM
GERONTE Project Manager	<i>Pending</i>	University of Bordeaux, FRANCE
Invited observers ad hoc		
Ad hoc observers may be invited as needed, e.g. to provide specific expertise or discuss specific matters.		

Appendix 2: Agreement and competing interests form for TSC members

Streamlined geriatric and oncological evaluation based on IC technology for holistic patient-oriented healthcare management for older multimorbid patients (GERONTE)

Trial Steering Committee: Agreement to join the Trial Steering Committee as a member and disclosure of potential competing interests.

Please complete the following document and return original to the TSC Facilitator.
(please initial box to agree)

	I have read and understood the TSC Charter version xx.x, dated __/__/__
	I agree to join the Trial Steering Committee for this trial as a member
	I agree to treat all sensitive trial data and discussions confidentially

The avoidance of any perception that a member of a TSC may be biased in some fashion is important for the credibility of the decisions made by the TSC and for the integrity of the trials.

Potential competing interests should be disclosed via the TSC facilitator. In many cases simple disclosure up front should be sufficient.

No, I have no potential competing interests to declare

Yes, I have potential competing interests to declare (please detail below)

Please provide details of any potential competing interests:

Name: _____

Signed: _____

Date: _____

Appendix 3: Agreement and competing interests form for observers

Streamlined geriatric and oncological evaluation based on IC technology for holistic patient-oriented healthcare management for older multimorbid patients (GERONTE)

Trial Steering Committee: Agreement to join the Trial Steering Committee as a member and disclosure of potential competing interests.

Please complete the following document and return original to the TSC Facilitator.

(please initial box to agree)

I have received a copy of the TSC Charter version xx.x, dated __/__/__

I agree to treat as confidential any sensitive information gained during this meeting unless explicitly permitted

Potential competing interests should be disclosed via the TSC facilitator. In many cases simple disclosure up front should be sufficient.

No, I have no potential competing interests to declare

Yes, I have potential competing interests to declare (please detail below)

Please provide details of any potential competing interests:

Name: _____

Signed: _____

Date: _____

APPENDIX 2: Trial Management Team (TMT) charter

Trial Management Team (TMT) charter

Version 0.1 du 29/03/2022

GERONTE consortium FRONE and TWOBE Trials

Sponsors: Institut Bergonié (FRONE) and Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (TWOBE)

Coordinating Investigators: Pr Pierre Soubeyran (FRONE) and Pr Hans Wildiers (TWOBE)

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Clinical Trials Unit (CTU): EUCLID

Writing / revision	EUCLID CTU Project manager Dr Cécile Duchiron	<i>Date et Signature</i>
Validation	EUCLID CTU representative Dr Christine Schwimmer	<i>Date et Signature</i>
	Sponsor representative Pr Simone Mathoulin-Pelissier	<i>Date et Signature</i>
Approbation	Coordinating investigators FRONE trial: Pr Pierre Soubeyran TWOBE trial: Pr Hans Wildiers	<i>Date et Signature</i>
Diffusion	TMT members	

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1. Role

The Trial Management Team (TMT) is the operational team that undertakes the day-to-day management of the GERONTE consortium’s FRONE and TWOBE trials.

2. Members

The TMT consists of the following members: coordinating investigators, sponsor representatives, national coordinating team representatives, and sub-study representatives, CTU representatives, EUCLID trial study team, safety officer (where appropriate).

The nominative list of the TMT members is detailed in Appendix 1 and kept updated by EUCLID.

3. Functioning

The TMT meets either by tele/visioconferences or Face-To-Face. Additional participants may be invited as appropriate. Meetings are organised by EUCLID.

Regular meetings

Regular meetings are usually held at monthly intervals although may be needed more frequently in the critical phases of the trial, and less frequently when enrolment is closed and there are no specific issues arising. Effort will be made to gather most if not all members at each meeting. Maintaining a regular meeting pattern takes precedence over the presence of all members, i.e. meetings should not be postponed or cancelled for > 2 months, except in exceptional circumstances. Announcing the schedule of meetings several weeks or months in advance and advertising the next meetings at each meeting is the mean used to help all members booking their own agenda for this specific meeting.

The primary objective of regular meetings is to share concise reporting of all activities. Reporting may include updates on regulatory status per country, updates on study documents, distribution of inclusions per site, recruitment difficulties, participants with discontinuation of follow-up, monitoring visits, safety matters if applicable, and any other relevant trial management activities. In each phase of the trial, the agenda follows a predefined scheme whenever possible.

Each member/entity is responsible for the preparation of documents and reporting regarding the activities he or she coordinates. All relevant documents for the meeting are made available to the

participants at least 2 days before the meeting. Each contributor uses a standardised report form (Trial Management Report) to report on the progress of the trial regarding their activities.

Extraordinary meetings

Extraordinary (ad-hoc) meetings may be convened in case of urgent matters. In this case the agenda of the meeting is to be adapted to the circumstances.

Document exchange

Minutes from TMT meetings or TMT reports are recorded by EUCLID, circulated to the TMT group and approved at the beginning of the next meeting.

4. Accountability

The TMT is accountable to the Trial Steering Committee, and to the Trial sponsors for specific matters such as budget.

Minutes or TMT reports are made available to sponsors and TSC members.

5. Decision making

Whenever possible, decision is reached by a consensus of the TMT members. When this is not possible, the final decision lies with the Trial Steering Committee for missions defined in the TSC charter, and with the trial sponsor for specific matters, such as budget.

6. Interaction with other Trial Committees

The TMT (represented by the TMT chair) formally reports to the Trial Steering Committee (TSC) on the progress of the trial periodically. This takes place at the regular meetings of the TSC, but any interim urgent issues will be communicated to the Chairman of the TSC as they arise, and the Chairman ensures appropriate communication to the TSC with ad-hoc meetings organised if needed.

APPENDIX 1 – Trial Management Team

Chair of the TMT: Hans Wildiers

Co-Chair: Pierre Soubeyran

➤ **Members**

	Members
Coordinating investigator TWOBE, PI Belgium	Hans Wildiers
Coordinating investigator FRONE, PI France	Pierre Soubeyran
Principal Investigator TWOBE The Netherlands, geriatric expert	Marije Hamaker
Sponsor representatives	Simone Mathoulin-Pelissier <i>KUL representative pending</i>
Substudy leaders	Lucia Ferrara
	Anthony Staines
EUCLID CTU Executive Director	Christine Schwimmer
EUCLID CTU Operations Manager	Cédric Wallet
Methodologist	Florence Saillour-Glenisson
Junior Methodologists	Julie Arsандаux Florence Francis
Senior project Manager	Caroline Lalet
Project Manager (facilitator)	Cécile Duchiron
KUL representative, BE and NL sites coordinator	Lien Degol
KUL site Advance Practice Nurse	Cindy Kenis
Coordinating Clinical Research Associate	TBD
Statistician	Marion Kret
Data manager	TBD
GERONTE project manager	<i>Pending</i>

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